

MATEMATIKA FANINI RIVOJLANISH DAVRLARI
MASALASIDAN

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Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani

2 son kasb hunar maktabi matematika fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada matematikaning rivojlanishi qadimiy ekanligi, aniq fan sifatida geometriya bilan bog'liqligi, sonlarni cheksiz va chekli xolatlari haqida fikrlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Sanoq, cheksiz, figura, hisoblash, bilim.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается древнее развитие математики, ее связь с геометрией как точной наукой, бесконечными и конечными состояниями чисел.

Ключевые слова: Счет, бесконечность, цифра, расчет, знание.

Abstract: The article discusses the ancient development of mathematics, its connection with geometry as an exact science, and the infinite and finite states of numbers.

Keywords: Counting, infinity, figure, calculation, knowledge.

Matematikaning paydo bo'lish davr juda qadim zamonlardan boshlanib to miloddan avvalgi VII— V asrlargacha davom etgan. Ilk ajdodlarimiz narsalarni sanash, ularni ayirboshlash, keyinchalik savdo-sotiq, yerni ulchash, fazoviy figuralar xdjmini xisoblash kabi ishlarni bajarish bilan shugullanib, matematik bilimlarni paydo kilganlar. Dastlabki matematik bilimlar amaliy xarakterga ega bulgan. Masalan, odamlar dekkonchilikdan olgan maxsulotlarni, yasagan asbob-uskunalarni, ovlangan x,ayvonlar, parranda va darrandalarni, shuningdek, boshka chekli sondagi narsalarni sanash bilan son tushunchasini yaratganlar. Son tushunchasi asrlar davomida matematikaning asosiy tushunchasiga aylangan.

Kishilar masofalar uzunligini, shakllar yuzini, jismlar x,ajmini, x,avo x,aroratini, hosilning oz-ko'pligini, predmetlarning vaznini va boshqa narsalarni o'lchash, sanash va takkoslash bilan mikdor tushunchasini yaratganlar. Mikdor va son tushunchalari uzviy x,olatda rivojlanib, takomillashib borgan. Bu tushunchalar asrlar utishi bilan shaklan ixchamlashib, ularga oid bilimlar mazmunan boyib borgan. Keyinchalik kishilar kisoblash ishlarida natural son va mikdor tushunchalaridan foydalanib, ish natijalarini tasvirlovchi mikdorlarni sonlar bilan ifodalaganlar.

Kishilar narsalarni sanash bilan kanoatlanmasdan, balki ulchash, kisoblash, kilingan ish natijalarini teng bo'laklarga taksimlash kabi ishlarni ham bajarganlar. Natijada butun sonni kasr kurinishda belgilash va kasr sonlar ustida amallar bajarish ektiyoji turila borgan. Xar kqnday butun sonni kasr son ko'rinishida yozish mumkin bulganidan kasr sonlar ustida amallar bajarish tartibi butun sonlar ustida bajariladigan amallar tartibini o'zida to'la saqlaydi. Kuzatish va oddiy muxrkama yuritish asosida odamlar uchburchak, kupburchak, doyra kabi tekis shakllar yuzini, turri parallelepiped, silindr kabi fazoviy jismlar x,ajmi va sirtini kisoblash bilan geometrik shakllardagi elementlarning mikdoriy kattaligini aniklovchi formulalar chikarganlar. Bu formulalar arifmetika va geometriyani Uzaro uzviy boglovchi yagona kuprik bulib, ulardagi materiallarni urganishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratgan.

Keyinchalik matematikaning kullanish doirasi kengaydi va boshlangich matematik bilimlarni tuplash davri boshlandi. Fan namoyandalari maajud bulgan matematik bilimlarni to'plashga va ularni ma'lum soxalar bo'yicha sistemalashtirishga kirishdilar. Shu tariqa qadimgi Misrda, X,indistonda, Xitoyda, Yunonistonda arifmetik va geometrik bilimlar yig'ila borib fan sifatida shakllangan.

Savdo-sotiqning rivojlanishi, koinot sirlarini \$fganishga intilishning ortib borishi, algebraik va geometrik bilimlar paydo bulishi va yigilib borishi — elementar matematika davri boshlanganidan darak beradi. Keyinchalik matematik

bilimlar mazmunan kengayib, arifmetika, geometriya, algebra, trigonometriya kabi mustakil fan tarmoklariga bulinib ketdi. Bu davr matematikasining katta yutuklaridan ba'zilari muntazam turtburchakli kesik piramida kurinishidagi jismlarning x,ajmini x,isoblash formulasini chikarish va 1 sonining kiymatini taqriban $(16:9)^2$ ga tengligini aniklash kabi natijalar hisoblanadi. Geometriyaning sistemali bayon qilinishi matematika fanining mantiqiy tuzilishiga asos buldi. Bu davrda son tushunchasini keng miqyosda urganishdan sonlar nazariyasi kelib chiqdi va sferik trigonometriya fani yaratildi.

O'zgarmas miqdor matematikasi davri. Bu davr (miloddan avvalgi VII asrdan to milodning XVII asrigacha) matematikasi ba'zi adabiyotlarda elementar matematika davri deb atalgan. Bu davr boshlaridayunon olimlari matematik bilimlarni mazmuniga qarab biror konuniyat asosida sistemali bayon kilishga va ularning kakikatligini mantiqiy muloxdzalar yuritib isbotlashga intilganlar. Bu esa kadimgi yunon matematiklarining fan yutuklarini sistemalashtirishda erishgan katta muvaffakiyatlari xisoblanadi. Qadimgi Misr olimlari xdm kupgina yangi matematik goyalarni isbot qilganlar.

Keyinchalik matematik fikrlarning oddiy va murakkabligiga karab aksioma, teorema kabi tushunchalar qabul qilingan. Boshda aksioma va teoremlarning xaqiqatligini tasdiqlovchi deduktiv isbotlash usullari paydo bo'lib, ular bizgacha yetib kelmagan. Ammo birinchi davrning oxirlarida yashab ijod etgan matematik olimlarning ishlari va ular kakidagi ba'zi ma'lumotlar uzuk-yuluk kolatda bizgacha

yetib kelgan. Masalan, yunon olimlaridan milotlik Fales (Milot — Kichik Osiyo shax,arlaridan biri) uz asarlarida tengyonli uchburchak asosidagi burchaklarning tengligini, vertikal burchaklarning tengligini, uchburchaklarning tenglik alomatlarini iligini tasdiqlovchi isbotlash usullarini keltiradi. Fales ishlatgan mantiliy fikr yuritish asosidagi matematik fikrlarni isbotlash usullari keyinchalik Pifagor va uning shogirdlari tomonidan yanada takomillashtirilgan.

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